

Full Research Paper

Optimizing data collection planning for Living Labs' access and effectiveness

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Abstract

This paper introduces a framework to optimize data collection planning in studies conducted within Living Labs. It emphasizes identifying what additional data—beyond the main study datasets—should be gathered to assess the effectiveness of Living Labs when accessed by external researchers or innovators. The framework is informed by the VITALISE project, in which 116 external researchers utilized Living Lab services across 56 Research Infrastructure Access studies. It outlines the types of data collected, such as services requested, researcher and staff time investment, and expectations before and after the studies. The framework details both individual dataset outputs and the insights gained from analyzing combined datasets. The findings aim to support a deeper understanding of how Living Labs function as research infrastructures and how their impact can be effectively measured.

Key words

Living Labs, Research infrastructure, services, effectiveness, data collection framework, access

Introduction

Living Labs are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments based on a systematic user co-creation approach that integrates research and innovation activities in communities, placing citizens at the centre of innovation (Vervoort et al. 2022). By engaging diverse stakeholders from the quadruple helix, including public, private, academia and citizens, living labs foster the development of innovations that are not only evidence-based but also tailored to the needs and contexts of end-users.

Living Labs exist in various forms (Alavi et al. 2020) and operate across a variety of 20 domains (Desole et al. 2023) including social innovation, health and well-being, smart cities and regions, education and vocational training and environmental and climate change. They are shifting from a project-based model to providing ongoing services for SMEs, researchers, and public authorities (Santonen, Petsani, Petronikolou, et al. 2024). A recent study by (Santonen, Petsani, Petronikolou, et al. 2024) introduced a classification of health and well-being Living Lab services to support ongoing discussions on their management. This categorization includes eight key service areas: (i) testing and validation, (ii) community and network building, (iii) project planning and management, (iv) co-creation, (v) capacity building, (vi) advisory services, (vii) market and sales support, and (viii) infrastructure and data management. However, given that Living Labs operates across multiple domains, another study (Santonen, Petsani, Bamidis, et al. 2024) explored their services beyond health and found that only one out of 18 services differed between sectors.

Despite their growing popularity, the effectiveness of accessing Living Labs' services remains understudied. This paper highlights the importance of systematically gathering and analyzing data from living lab studies to evaluate their services' access effectiveness and customer satisfaction. By doing so, we aim to provide a framework for harmonizing the collection of data beyond the main study's datasets, towards evaluating the effectiveness of a Living Lab when being accessed by researchers/innovators.

Access to Living Labs as Research Infrastructures

Research Infrastructures (RIs) provide researchers with access to facilities, resources, and expertise available within these infrastructures. Access to RI services is governed by access policy documents (ESFRI 2019), which define eligibility criteria and the applicable rules and principles. Additionally, RIs ensure transparency in promoting and disseminating their services by offering clear information on their equipment, costs, fees,

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contractual obligations, health, safety, and environmental procedures, intellectual property rights, and legal dispute resolution. Through access services (ESFRI Working Group on Monitoring of Research Infrastructures Performance 2019) RI resources may be made available to a broader research community, enabling researchers to conduct experiments, gather data, or perform analyses. Access policies may vary, with some RIs opting for selective access based on specific criteria. Excellence-driven access is granted based on peer-reviewed scientific merit, while market-driven access involves a fee, with the possibility of study outcomes remaining confidential and some of the services being offered for open access.

In recent years, Living Labs have emerged as robust research and innovation infrastructures, playing a crucial role in integrating research and innovation processes within real-life settings. These labs prioritize people and their active participation in research activities. They span the entire innovation cycle, from the initial design thinking phase to scaling innovations for market adoption. By supporting researchers in formulating research questions and facilitating the transition of innovations to commercialization, Living Labs distinguishes itself from traditional laboratory environments.

Unlike conventional labs, Living Labs operate in real-world settings, ranging from isolated locations to broader environments such as schools, residential areas, workplaces, and even entire cities or urban districts (Hossain et al. 2019). Alavi et al. (Alavi et al. 2020) identified five distinct types of Living Labs. Visited Places, and laboratories equipped with sensors and monitoring devices to replicate typical living spaces. Instrumented Places, are real-world environments where sensors and monitoring devices are installed, allowing short-term participation from residents. Instrumented People are individuals who agree to wear monitoring devices or use smartphone applications to track their daily activities or specific behaviours. Lived-in Places, Functional environments such as offices, schools, and residential buildings designed for long-term and continuous research programs. And Innovation Spaces, Collaborative hubs where stakeholders from various sectors work together to promote participatory design and democratized innovation, fostering grassroots-driven solutions. These diverse forms of Living Labs facilitate innovation by blending real-world interactions with structured research, ensuring that advancements are both practical and people centered.

A Living Lab's collaborative environment can take shape in virtually any setting, from museums, hospitals, and schools to sports fields, forests, agricultural lands, or even entire cities. Beyond fostering co-creation and teamwork, Living Labs leverage real-world

experimental settings to continuously assess how innovations are adopted over time. This ongoing evaluation process generates valuable insights for all stakeholders involved, ensuring that new solutions are both practical and sustainable in the long run.

There have been limited efforts in the literature to systematically describe and categorize the services offered by Living Labs (Eschenbächer et al. 2010)(Santonen et al. 2020). The PREPSOIL project sought to address this gap by compiling a comprehensive list of Soil Living Lab services through an extensive literature review and collaborative activities with stakeholders (Cerezo Soto et al. 2024).

Similarly, the VITALISE project has developed a wiki platform (<https://wiki.livinglab-harmonization.com>) that provides an evolving database of services offered by health and wellbeing Living Labs. This resource is based on findings from existing research (Santonen et al. 2020)(Santonen, Petsani, Petronikolou, et al. 2024)(Santonen, Petsani, Bamidis, et al. 2024) and goes beyond simple listing by offering detailed descriptions of each service. The goal is to create a shared understanding among Living Labs and assist researchers in setting realistic expectations for their projects. Key services available for accessing Living Lab resources include data access, co-creation workshops and sessions, proof-of-concept testing and feasibility studies, equipment and facility rental, Impact assessments, legal, regulatory, and safety compliance guidance, participant panel management, small- and large-scale pilot studies and usability testing. By offering these services, Living Labs provide a structured framework for research and innovation, enabling more effective collaboration and real-world experimentation.

Evaluating Living Lab Effectiveness

There is significant interest in assessing the effectiveness of Living Labs when accessed by researchers and innovators, as this evaluation can create opportunities for further enhancement. By systematically evaluating their access, Living Labs can optimize resource utilization, ensuring efficient and effective use to improve the user experience. Such evaluations help identify user needs and challenges, enabling improvements in the services and support provided. This not only enhances the overall experience and satisfaction for researchers and innovators who initiate the studies but also for participants actively involved, such as citizens and the public. Additionally, systematic evaluation can elevate research quality by ensuring researchers and innovators have effective access to tools and services, allowing them to focus on the core aspects of their studies.

This paper proposes a framework designed to optimize data collection planning for evaluating the access and effectiveness of Living Labs. The framework outlines the types of data that should be collected before, during, and after a study to better understand how this data can assess Living Labs' effectiveness, including aspects like sustainability, innovation, and user satisfaction. The framework is based on insights and experiences gained by the authors during the implementation of the VITALISE project as well as the on-going projects EVOLVE2CARE⁹ and FARCLIMATE¹⁰ which are applying and building on top of these principles.

Living Labs' access effectiveness data collection in VITALISE

The VITALISE project was one of the pioneering initiatives aimed at opening up Living Lab research infrastructures to support and advance research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain across Europe and beyond. To achieve this, VITALISE facilitated in-person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab Research Infrastructures, as well as remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) in areas such as rehabilitation, transitional care, and everyday living environments. This was made possible through harmonized processes and shared tools. The project's primary goal was to identify the key services and procedures that Living Labs can offer as Research Infrastructures (RIs) and to validate the concept of Living Labs functioning as RIs. VITALISE aimed to provide researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain with a) convenient access to research infrastructures, b) direct engagement with people (citizens, patients, etc.) to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, assess feasibility and effectiveness and c) cross-disciplinary expertise to address the complexities of Health and Wellbeing research.

The ultimate beneficiaries of VITALISE included the broader Health and Wellbeing research community, as well as innovation and industry stakeholders. As part of the project, three Open Calls were launched (Petsani et al. 2022)(Santonen et al. 2022)(Bernaerts et al. 2022), inviting researchers to apply for access to Living Lab research infrastructures. Each infrastructure offered customized services, such as methodological support, access to specialized equipment, expert consultations, and assistance with participant recruitment and data analysis. These services were essential in enabling visiting researchers to effectively carry out their planned activities. In total, 116 external researchers accessed Living Lab services to conduct 56 Research Infrastructure Access studies. Throughout these studies, data was collected before, during, and after each project, including details on the services requested and utilized, the hours worked

⁹ <https://evolve2care.eu>

¹⁰ <https://farclimate-project.eu>

by researchers and Living Lab personnel, and pre- and post-study expectations, among other datasets.

Optimization and Planning for Data Collection Ensuring Data Quality and Integrity

This section presents the proposed framework for data collection planning for Living Labs' access and effectiveness in the form of type of data and when to be collected, the source of the data as well as whether the data is quantitative or qualitative. The 5 data collection phases presented in here correspond to the i) Living Labs' offering, ii) application and selection phase, iii) after selection and before access phase, iv) during the access period and v) after the access period, following living lab process from customer touch point to project implementation as proposed by Santonen et al. (Santonen, Petsani, Petronikolou, et al. 2024)

Living Labs' offering

The Living Labs' offering corresponds to the characteristics of the Living Lab in terms for services and devices. These are integral parts of Living Lab's marketing and communication assets making visible what a Living Lab can offer their customers. It is based on the capacity and expertise of a Living Lab and can potentially affect the feasibility of a study.

The services portfolio collects information about the services provided by the Living Lab. According to (Santonen, Petsani, Petronikolou, et al. 2024), which is generalized for the different types of Living Labs (Santonen, Petsani, Bamidis, et al. 2024), the living lab services consists of four phases: customer acquisition, detailed project planning, project implementation and dissemination and, innovation ecosystem orchestration. Services are classified into the following three categories: back-office services (administrative and support functions), research & development services (collaborative generation of new knowledge), and auxiliary services (auxiliary processes for ensuring safe and ethical living lab operations).

The devices portfolio refers to the tools and devices provided by the Living Labs for digital data collection and intervention. A recent study on categorizing digital data collection and intervention tools in health and wellbeing living lab settings through a modified Delphi study (Petsani et al. 2024) concluded in the following categories: environment monitoring, human monitoring, assistive technology, extended reality – XR, VR & AR and serious

games. A study by Santonen et. Al (Santonen, Petsani, Konstantinidis, et al. 2024) shows an example how taxonomy can be used for evaluating device usage in Living Lab projects.

Application and selection phase

This is the phase during which researchers and innovators submit proposals or applications outlining their intended use of the LL's resources. This step, is followed by the evaluation and selection phase, resembling the excellence-driven access approach where access is granted based on a peer-review process.

The access application, apart from information on the researcher group experience, collects information about the proposed study's objectives and methodology, the required devices, participants' involvement, time periods and ethics requirements. For Living Lab studies, research protocols for interventions should be defined based on the Template for Intervention Description and Replication (TIDieR) checklist and guidelines (Hoffman et al., 2024), as it provides a clear and universal way to communicate as the example by Santonen et al (Santonen et al. 2022) presents. During the application phase, the applicants describe the services that will be requested by the Living Lab. If the same application targets more than one Living Lab, different services might be requested by the different Living Labs. During the study implementation, the services provided might be different from the ones requested in the application as this stage reflects the understanding of the applicants in terms of Living Lab services.

The Access applications evaluation is composed of the eligibility check, meeting any specific criteria set by the Living Lab, the feasibility evaluation where the requested services and resources are checked against the Living Lab's offerings, and finally the excellence evaluation, especially in case of applications competing for limited resources from the Living Lab. During the feasibility evaluation, a negotiation phase among the Living Lab managers and the applicants might take place towards turning a not-feasible application into feasible by considering both sides' needs and capacity.

After selection and before the access phase

This stage corresponds to the preparation phase of the study, involving refinement of the protocol based on the Living Lab's offerings as well as the preparation and submission of the ethical application whenever needed as external participants are usually actively involved.

Expectations for access refer to the pre-access expectations from TA researchers after their application has been selected and any discussion/negotiation with the Living Lab

manager took place. The expectations collection refers to the quality and quantity of the services they will be provided with by the Living Lab.

The study protocol refers to the methodology that the visiting researchers will apply with a focus on the number of iterations, the participants involved per iteration as well as the data that will be collected. This combination affects the ethical application which is usually mandatory for Living Lab studies (as external people are involved in).

The ethical application is usually prepared by the Living Lab personnel considering the study protocol. Any comment or feedback from the ethical committee is useful to be collected as it could save time from the following studies with similar protocols.

During the access period

This is the phase where the actual Living Lab access is happening. Either in-person or remotely, the visiting researchers as using the resources of the Living Lab.

The Feedback of the introductory training concerns the training offered by the Living Lab to the visiting researchers on how to use the living lab's services.

Periodic feedback from researchers collects information on the researchers' activities performed during the visit. This feedback can be organized as a weekly diary and could also involve services used, datasets collected, user experience and difficulties encountered.

After the access period

This is the follow-up data collection from the visiting researchers, the participants and the Living Lab's personnel as far as participation experience is concerned and resources' actual usage. This is the more critical phase as it corresponds to the implementation of the study and can provide insight and conclusions based on the reality. This justifies the fact that this phase includes more data collection items than any of the previous phases.

The feedback from visiting researchers on their research experience collects information about the actual experience and satisfaction of using the Living Lab services. More specifically, the collected information deals with how well the Living Lab meets their expectations in several domains such as methodology, user recruitment, what they gained from their access and what they appreciated most. It also contains suggested improvements for the Living Lab. Similarly, the feedback from the living lab personnel is

about the experience and satisfaction of the personnel that served and supported the visiting researchers during accessing the Living Labs.

The usage resources data corresponds to the Living Lab resources used in time. Hours engaged for each of the visiting researchers per day, separating the in-person and remote engagement. For the Living Lab's personnel, the hours worked for supporting the access should be counted per day for each of the different roles (Living Lab manager, technician, administrative, etc.).

The services usage reflects the actual services used. This is reported by the Living Lab and can be compared against the services requested information that has been provided by the visiting researcher during the application and selection phase. In the same context, the devices use reflects the actual devices used for the TA research study which could deviated from the initial plan during the application phase.

As Living Labs usually involve participants from their panels (stakeholders from the quadruple helix), their feedback on the experience and satisfaction during their recruitment and involvement in the Living Labs activities plays a crucial role in the long-term engagement strategy.

Finally, the innovation capacity evaluates the innovation potential of the results as well as the study outcomes up taking from the Living Lab for future studies.

Discussion

This study has presented a comprehensive framework for data collection planning within Living Labs, emphasizing the importance of aligning data collection strategies with the specific characteristics and operational dynamics of Living Labs, ensuring that both qualitative and quantitative data are systematically gathered to evaluate access effectiveness and operational efficiency.

The first phase, Living Labs' offering, highlights the critical role of understanding the services and devices provided by Living Labs. The application and selection phase underscores the importance of a rigorous evaluation process, including eligibility checks, feasibility assessments, and excellence evaluations, to ensure that the most promising and well-aligned projects are granted access. The after-selection and before-access phase focuses on the refinement of study protocols and ethical considerations, which are crucial for ensuring the integrity and compliance of research activities. The during the access period phase captures the real-time experiences and feedback of visiting

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researchers, providing valuable insights into the practical challenges and successes of utilizing Living Lab resources. Finally, the after-access period phase provides a comprehensive evaluation of the overall experience and outcomes of the research project. This includes feedback from visiting researchers, Living Lab personnel, and participants, as well as an assessment of resource usage and innovation potential. The data collected in this phase is essential for informing future studies and enhancing the long-term engagement and impact of Living Labs.

The proposed framework offers a systematic and structured approach to data collection planning in Living Labs, ensuring that all relevant aspects of access and effectiveness are thoroughly evaluated. By aligning data collection strategies with the operational phases of Living Labs, this framework supports the continuous improvement of Living Lab operations and the successful implementation of innovative research projects. Future research should focus on the application and validation of this framework across different types of Living Labs to further refine and enhance its effectiveness.

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